

Rural Youth Livelihood Choice and Access to Land in Bauchi State, Nigeria

Yusuf, A.¹, Adamu, S.F.² and Zailani, I.³

¹Department of Agricultural Extension and Management, Bauchi State College of Agriculture, Bauchi, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Extension and Management, Bauchi State College of Agriculture, Bauchi, Nigeria

³Department of Crop Production Technology, Bauchi State College of Agriculture, Bauchi, Nigeria

Author contact:abdullahiyusuf1987@gmail.com

Abstract

Nigeria is bestowed with favourable farming land and other natural resources capable of employing youth and makes the country food secured. Therefore, the study investigated rural youth determinants' of livelihood choice between farming and non-farming and access to land in the study area. The study adopted multiple sampling procedures in stages to select 360 rural youth. Data collection was through the use of questionnaire, and was analysed using percentage; binary logistic regression and mean score. The results show farming was the livelihood choice for 60.6% of the respondents. Result from binary logistic regression shows: Gender (1.080); years of education (-0.102); parent occupation (1.288) and youth access to land were the main determinants for youths livelihood choice between farming and non-farming. In term of access to land, 50.3% of the respondents have an access to land of an average mean size of 1.4 hectare through inheritance (49.2%), purchase (30.1%) and rent (15.0%). Lack of fund, non-availability of land, high cost of purchasing and renting land, reliant on inheritance were perceived as the most severed constraint to youth access to land in the study area. If farming is modernised in rural areas through effective policies and programmes that ensure equitable access to productive resources such as land and other inputs irrespective of youth socio-economic status, that could be a breakthrough in addressing youth unemployment and food insecurity among other social problems in Nigeria.

Keywords: Rural, youth, land, livelihood

INTRODUCTION

Poverty and food security are key issues militate developing countries that attract attention of national governments and international agencies. The economies of these countries particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa are agric dependent, and characterised with low productivity (Philip, 2023). Nigeria as an oil producing country, agriculture remains the backbone of the economy, contributes 22.35 % of the total gross domestic product and employs over 60% of the population (FAO, 2023). Countries that depend heavily on agriculture may not likely create sufficient jobs for youth outside agricultural sector. Therefore, employing youth in agriculture will be vital for food security and economic development of these countries.

But do the youths have an interest in agriculture, particularly farming? What factors determine their livelihood choice between farming and non-farming? If they have an interest in farming, do they have an access to land that is a key capital in farming?

Agricultural sector is in position that direct and indirectly accelerates socioeconomic and industrial development of a country. Despite the recognition of this potential, internationally and nationally, literature points to the decline of youth interest and engagement in farming (Kumeh and Omulo, 2019). The decline and lack of interest in farming was due to lack of access to land; market; information and education; adequate financial support, and poor return of farming, low social status of farmers and farming business in communities (Yaboah et al., 2020; Bello et al., 2021).

Land is a basic source of livelihood, key agricultural input and a major determinant for access to other productive resources and service (Mauto, 2022). Access to land is mostly guided through land tenure system operate in the country. Land tenure is the bundle of rights and responsibilities assigned among people, as individual or group with respect to ownership and use of land resources through a common law or customary law (FAO, 2023). Securing land right for young people can create pathways for youth to take part in developing rural economies; with increase access and control over productive landholdings, rural youth are more likely to be food producers than migrate to urban areas (Mauto, 2022). Access to land is highly important particularly for youth in rural areas of northern Nigeria where farming is a main mean of livelihood. Youth in rural areas face greater challenge to access land than adult, because, youth mostly access land through inheritance, however, shortage of land, increase in household size and life expectancy have rendered it ineffective (Onya et al., 2019 and Moreda, 2023). The challenges for youth access to land vary between communities, regions, countries and continents, and are poorly documented. According to Yaboah et al. (2019) and International Land Coalition (ILC) (2023) Unfavourable land tenure systems and customary practices; over reliance on inheritance; poor sale and rental land markets; lack of funds to buy or rent land; inadequate access to information; lack of legal protection of rights for youth and lack of youth consideration in state-sponsored land redistribution programs are the most prominent challenges constraint youth access to land. Therefore, any agenda to attract rural young people in to farming has to ensure youth have access to land in rural areas. Scientific knowledge on factors determines youth livelihood choice between farming and non-farming, and access to land will provide guidance in policy formulation to address youth unemployment and food insecurity in rural areas and country at large. The scanty type of this scientific information in the Bauchi state, Nigeria, necessitates this study to investigate the factors determine rural youth livelihood choice and access to land in the study area.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Bauchi state. The state is located between latitudes 9° 3' and 12° 3' north and longitudes 8° 50' and 11° east, occupies a total land area of 49,119 km². The state was agriculturally divided into three zones based on the climatic conditions that varied across the region: western agricultural zone; central and northern zone. The state has an average temperature of 35 degree Celsius with rainfall ranges from 700 mm per annum in the north to 1,300 mm per annum in the south. The state has an estimated population of 6,537, 300 persons in which 32.9% were between the ages of 15-35 years old, mostly resided in rural areas (NBS, 2019) Small scale agriculture was the dominant economic activity in the state (BSADP, 2022).

The population of the study were youth (ages of 15 to 25 years old); reside in rural areas of Bauchi state, Nigeria. The population was sampled through random sampling procedure in stages. In stage I: Two local government areas were randomly selected from northern agricultural zone, central and western zone. In stage II: Three villages where both rain-fed and irrigation farming practiced were purposely selected from each selected local government area. In stage III: Twenty youth were randomly selected from each selected village that gave three hundred and sixty (360) youth as samples for the study.

The data was collected between May to October, 2018, with the use of structured questionnaire. The data was collected on socio-economic characteristics of the youth, livelihood choice, land ownership, mode of land access and constraints to access to land. The data were analysed using frequency, percentage mean score, and binary logistic regression model. The Logistic regression model is a statistical probability model with two categories in the dependent variable.

The binary logistic regression model was used in this study to analyse the determinants of rural youth livelihood choice between farming and non-farming.

Youth livelihood choice between farming and non-farming was a dependent variable in this study; and was captured as dummy variable with the value of 1 assigned to choice of farming while 0 was assigned to choice of non-farming occupation. The model is specified as $P(Y = 1/X_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_i X_i$, $\mu_i = 1, 2, \dots, n$...

Where: $P_i = P(Y = 1/X_i)$ is the probability of the i^{th} youth choice of farming and $Y = 1$ means choice of farming ; $Y = 0$ means choice non-farming

X_i = explanatory variables,

β_0 = the intercept

β_i = the corresponding coefficient and

U_i = error term

n = sample size

Table 1: Variables used in the model, their Units and expected Signs

Variable	Measurement	Expected sign
Gender (X1)	Male= 1 Female=0	+
Age (X2)	In years	+
Marital status (X3)	Married=1 Unmarried=0	+
Household size (X4)	Number of persons	+
Educational level (X5)	In years	-
Parents 'occupation (Male) (X6)	Farming=1 Otherwise =0	+
Family ownership of land(X7)	Family owned land=1 Not owned=0	+
Youth ownership of land (X8)	Youth owned land=1 Not owned=0	+

Results and discussions

Results from Table 1 below shows majority (75%) of the respondents were male. In far north Nigeria, females usually handle domestic work at home while males deal with the economic activities outside home to provide for the homes needs, this limit the number of female engaged in farming and less accessible.

Table 2: Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents (N=360)

Variable	Level	Percentage	Mean
Gender	Male	75	
	Female	25	
Age in years	15-20	47.4	
	21-25	18.0	
	26 -30	34.6	22.5
Marital status	Single	33.9	
	Married	66.1	
Household size	Less than 3	70.9	
	3-5	27.2	
	6 and above	1.9	1.7
Education	Illiterate	48.9	
	Primary	12.5	
	Secondary	28.6	
	Tertiary	10.0	
Parent occupation	Farming	70.3	
	Business	18.1	
	Civil servant	5.3	
	Artisan	6.3	
Youth livelihood choice	Farming	60.6	

Non-farming 39.4

Source: Field Survey. 2019

The respondents have an average mean age of 22.5 years old. This indicated they were in energetic age characterised with strength and commitment. 66.1% of the respondents were married with average household size member of 1.7. Marriage is an important social status that allow access to family productive resources such as land in rural areas, this contribute to early marriage in rural areas. Moreover, 51.1% of the respondents attended formal education, where majority (28.6%) have secondary school certificate. Education has been shown to be a factor in the adoption of agricultural innovations and employability in the formal sector (Kafando et al., 2022). Farming was the major occupation for 70.3% parent of the respondents. According to FAO (2022) farming is the dominant economic activity in rural areas of Sub-Saharan Africa. The Table 2 above further reveals the livelihood choice of the respondents, where farming was livelihood choice for 60.6% of the respondent.

Determinants of rural youth livelihood choice

Four out of eight independents variables tested were found significant, the three significant variables (gender, parent occupation access to land) positively determined the choice of farming while years of education negatively determined the choice of farming as a livelihood mean. The findings are summarised in Table 3 below.

Gender and youth occupational choice

Gender plays greater role in agriculture and determines the livelihood choice of an individual in rural areas of developing countries. Result from the binary regression in Table 3 below shows gender significantly influenced the choice of farming occupation as a mean of livelihood. As 75% of the respondents were male, the coefficient of gender reveals that male has chances of being a farmer than female. This can be attributed to gender disparity in access to productive resources particularly land. Another factor might be due to physical labour requires in farming while male can do tedious work than female. This agrees with (Shahzat et al., 2021).

Table 3: Logistic estimation for youth livelihood choice (N=360)

Explanatory variable	Coefficient	Standard error	P>z
Sex	1.080	0.298	0.001***
Age in years	0.033	0.034	0.333
Years of education	-0.102	0.021	0.001***
Marital status	0.572	0.349	0.101
Household size	0.159	0.164	0.332
Parent occupation	1.288	0.290	0.001***
Family ownership of land	0.117	0.421	0.782
Youth ownership of land	0.699	0.275	0.011**
Constant	-3.130	0.876	0.001

Number of 360
observation

Source: Field Survey. 2019: $r^2=0.259$; adjusted $r^2=0.345$; ***=1%; **=5%

Yeas of education and youth livelihood choice

Regard to youth years of education, from the binary logistic regression, the coefficient of education (-0.102) reveals that youth without formal education is likely to be farmer than youth with formal education. Education is an important factor that shapes an individual conscience in choice of path for achieving his/her goal. Education is an important factor in agricultural production by creating mental attitude toward adoption of innovation. Education combine with other factors of production increases productivity, unfortunate, African youth in rural areas prefer non-farming jobs mostly in formal sector. This negatively affects agricultural production as farming was left to poor uneducated youth incapable of adopting and employing improve production techniques. The finding agrees with (Ochieng, 2020) that found education influenced youth moving away from farming.

Parent occupation and youth livelihood choice

Parent occupation significantly influences the choice of farming occupation as livelihood mean. The coefficient of parent occupation from the logistic result shows respondents from farming based house are likely to be a farmer than respondents from non-farming based house. The background and orientation of an individual's virtue of their parent's occupation influence his desire, interest and engagement. The finding is in line with (Olayemi and Emeka, 2021)

Youth access to land and livelihood choice

Access to land is extremely important for young people trying to earn a livelihood in agriculture. Result from binary regression in Table 3 below shows that youth land ownership significantly influences the choice of farming as a livelihood mean. This means that youth that owned a piece of farm land is more likely to be a farmer than youth that did not own land. The result is in agreement with the result Ochieng(2021) reported youth ownership of land influenced decision to be a farmer.

Rural youth access to land

Result from Table 4 below shows majority(88%) of the respondents reported their family possessed land, further, 50.3% of the youth possess their own farmlands of average mean size of 1.4 hectare, accessed through inheritance (49.2%), purchase (30.1%), lease(15.0%) and government (5.7)

Table 4: Respondents access to land (N=360)

variable	Level	Percentage
Family land ownership	Owned	88.0
	Not owned	12.0
Youth ownership of land	Owned	50.3
	Not owned	49.7
Youth land sizes owned	0.5 – 2.5	97.4
	2.6 -4.6	2.6 1.4
Mode of access to land	Inheritance	49.2
	Purchase	30.1
	Lease	15.0
	Government	5.7

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Land ownership entitled more land right, land right is a social or legal recognised entitlement to access, utilize and control areas of land. A community where farming is a major occupation, ownership of land has become necessarily and can serves as a tool for membership of associations and accession of credits and other productive assets. According to FAO (2022) the average landholding in Nigeria per farmer is 1.8 hectare, accessed through inheritance. Inheritance is the transfer of land entitlement and right from decedent to family members.

Constraints to Youth Access to Land

The results from Table 5 below shows lack of fund by the youth with a mean score of 4.57, was the most severed constraint for youth to access land. Youths mostly work on their farms or family farms that offer little or no payment at all due to limited off-farm income generating activities in rural areas, therefore, they could not earn enough funds to purchase or rent a viable land for a long-term period.

Table 5: Perceived constraints to youth access to land (N=360)

Variable	SD (\pm)	Mean	Rank
Lack of fund by youth to access land	0.68	4.57	1
High cost of Purchasing land	0.66	4.28	2
Reliant of youth on inheritance	1.02	3.89	3
High cost of renting land	0.96	3.85	4
Unwillingness of parent to share land with youth	0.98	3.84	5
High cost of leasing land	1.09	3.34	6
Non-availability of leasing land	1.07	3.28	7
Non-availability of purchasing	1.31	3.25	8
Non-availability of renting land	1.14	3.21	9
Difficulties in land transfer	1.34	2.90	10

Source: Field Survey, 2019

High cost of purchasing land (4.28) was ranked second most severed constraint; this could be due to high demand for farming lands by wealthy individuals and firms venturing in to food productions as a result of higher demand of food items at an increasing prices. Reliant on inheritance (3.89) were ranked third most severed constraints for youth to access land by the respondents. According to FAO (2022) life expectancy has increased in most developing countries; therefore, youth has to wait longer to inherit a parcel of family land. The results agree with (Yaboah et al., 2019).

Conclusion and Recommendation

The choice of farming as a means of livelihood by youths in rural areas was positively influenced by gender, parent occupation and access to land while years of education influenced the choice of other means of livelihood than farming in rural areas. Therefore, the study recommends policies and programmes that modernise farming, ensure both male and female youth's have an access to productive inputs particularly land, and incorporate practical farming in secondary school curriculum to attract educated youth in to farming business.

Land as an important factor that determine the choice of farming as a mean of livelihood, 50% of the youth have an access to land of not more than 1.5 hectare through inheritance, purchase and rent. The youth access to land is affected by ineffectiveness of inheritances as a major mode of access to land; inefficient sale and rental land market, youths lack fund in rural areas. The study recommends policies that ensure effective land market; off-farms income generating activities in rural areas, and youth should be considered in government sponsored land distribution programmes. The research suggests further study to investigate the relationship between education and youth engagement in agriculture in rural areas of developing countries.

Acknowledgement

I will like to acknowledge the Bauchi State Government for the funding of this research through Bauchi State Ministry of Education

Competing Interest

There is no competing interest in the study

References

- Bauchi State Ministry of Agriculture. 2022. Annual report. BSMARD, Bauchi, Nigeria.
- Bello, L.O., Baiyegunhi, S.J.M., Mignouna, D. Dontsop, N. P., Abdoulaye, T., Mayong, V., Bamba, Z., & Awotide, A. B. (2021). Impact of youth-in-agribusiness program on employment creation in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainability*, 13 (14), 1-20. Retrived January 13, 2021 from <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147801>
- FAO. 20202. Nigeria a glance. Retrived January 2021 from <http://www.fao.org/nigeria/fao-in-nigeria/nigeria-at-a/>
- FAO. 2022. Country fact sheet food and Agriculture policy trends. Retrived August 23, 2023 from www.fao.org
- Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nation. (2023). What is land tenure. Retrived February 3, 2021 from <https://www.fao.org/3/y4307e/y4307e05.htm>
- Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nation. (2023). Nigerian at glance: *Contribution of Agriculture to GDP in Nigeria*. Retrived March 23, 2021 <https://www.fao.org/Nigeria/fao-in-nigeria/en/>
- International Land Coalition (2023). The challenge of Youth land Right-Africa. Retrived March 17, 2023 from <https://africallandcoalition.org/en>
- Kafando, B., Essohannam, P., Kodjo T.G. (2022). Education and agricultural technology adoption in rural India. *International Journal of Research in Business Management Economic*, 1,(01), 53-74 Retrieved February 01, 2023 from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365267154>
- Kumeh E.K. and Omulo G. (2019) Youth access to agricultural land in sub-Saharan Africa: A missing linkage in the global land grabbing discourse. *Land Use Policy*, 89(01).
- Mauto T. (2022). Give land right to youth to booth rural economies; Landesa United States Seattle, Washington, D.C. Retrieved February 20, 2022, from <https://www.landesa.org>
- Moreda M. (2023) The social dynamics of access to land, livelihoods and the rural youth in an era of rapid rural change: Evidence from Ethiopia. *Land Use Policy, Elsevier*, C(128), 1-13.
- National Bureau of Statistics 2019. Nigeria socio-economic statistics (NBS), Abuja. Retrived December 19, 2020 from <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng/elibrary>
- Nelson Albert Ochieng. (2021). Are youth moving towards or away from agriculture in Tanzania. *Research on poverty alleviation programme limited* Retrieved August 21 from www.repoa.or.tz

- Olayemi S. S., Emeka O. (2021) Factor influencing the interest of youths toward carrier in agriculture Bwari area council, Abuja. *International Journal of Agricultural Research*, 9 (006) 61-68
- Onya, S.C., Ugochukwu, G.C. & Ejiba, I. V. (2019). Farm-level determinants of access to land by arable crop farmers in Ikwuano local government. *Journal of Tropical Agriculture, Food, Environment and Extension*, 18 (1), 50-55. Retrieved January 19 2021 from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/as/article/view/183842>
- Philip, W., Thomas, B., Yuchen, L., Christopher, U., & Douglas, G. (2023). Agricultural productivity growth in Africa: New evidence from microdata. Retrieved August 13, 2023 from World Bank. <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/ccfc87d5ab2c4af01f1887-005002202023>.
- Shahzad M. A., Abubakar S., Fscher C. (2021). Factors Affecting farm successor and occupational choices of nominated farm successors in Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. *Agriculture*, Retrieved March 23, 2022 from <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11121203>
- Yeboah F.K, Jayne T.M, Muyanga M. and Chamberlin J. (2020). Youth access to land Migration and employment opportunities: evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Papers of the 2019 Rural Development Report*. 53 IFAD Research series. <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract-id=3523765>